

Globalization processes and main directions of ideological threats in modernizing Uzbekistan.

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Abstract: It is not a secret to any of us that today the process of globalization continues rapidly. In this sense, it is becoming global and spiritual in today's world where various threats are increasing in the educational sphere the level of development of the dynamics of changes in our life, characteristic of it particular importance is attached to the implementation of laws and specific national characteristics related to this, moral threats, their rapid growth and finding a solution to them. In this article, the author describes in detail the process of globalization in modernizing Uzbekistan and the current moral threats and their main directions.

Key words: globalization, processes of globalization, national spirituality, value, moral threat, New Uzbekistan.

In the 21st century, humanity shows its uniqueness by achieving success in science and technology. As the development progresses, the process of globalization grows along with it. Globalization. It is a complex process that continues whether we like it or not. There is no way to avoid or avoid its influence. Therefore, it is appropriate to understand its true essence, to scientifically research its positive and negative effects for our society. It's hard to find a single industry that hasn't been affected by this process. Because in today's era, globalization has managed to show itself in all small points of the world. In most cases, the concept of globalization is considered as a change in the human society, material, spiritual, economic sphere and its results. Nowadays, there are many opinions about the concept of globalization. If we pay attention to the essence of this concept, according to Abu Nasr Farabi, he advocated such ideas as: "Each person strives to achieve the highest level of maturity. Such maturity is achieved through the urban community." Of course, globalization is an irreversible process that is happening all over the world. It is necessary and dangerous for us as well as other countries. But it should not be one-sided. Globalization does not mean the loss of national identity.

The globe has become what it is today under the influence of Western and Eastern globalization. The nations of the world strive to live in democratic societies

based on the principles of peace, stability, solidarity, and harmony. The common desire of billions of people living on earth is to preserve universal traditions and customs, preserve them, and stabilize national identity. However, moral threats make this impossible. As a result of the deepening of the globalization process, it has become dangerous for people various non-traditional threats are emerging. The most dangerous of these are people trace the values and way of life of nations by influencing their psyche which has a serious effect on morals, family and community life are moral threats Globalization - social life of different countries and peoples strong interaction and connection in the political, economic, and spiritual spheres is to increase.

There are many definitions of globalization. Based on them

The main features of the globalization process can be explained as follows:

- that globalization is a continuous historical process;
 - globalization - the process of homogenization and universalization of the world;
 - globalization - the process of "washing away" of national borders;
 - transition to international forms of production in production, acceleration of the movement of production factors;
 - uniform international standards in the economy of world countries
- introduction;
- in the culture and everyday life of most peoples of the country European way of life (westernization), American way of life
- manifestation;
- Globalization of investments, capital, technology and goods as a whole
- the flow around the world is accelerating and gaining a large scale be evaluated as a complex process;
- globalization is a mass movement that brings different nations closer together
- connection with fundamental changes caused by culture;
- globalization as a result of democratic processes all over the world
- to a rising standard of living and a significant reduction in poverty to be considered a contributing factor;

- globalization promotes productivity and additional work in exchange for expansion of opportunities, growth of the economy to be considered as an integrated process that creates places;

- globalization is closely related to the information revolution dependence and so on.

"New The 7th section of the work entitled "Uzbekistan Strategy" is "Uzbekistan and universal problems" and it says:

- Climate changes, environmental crises;
- The need to protect the island and mother nature;
- Radicalism, extremism and terrorism - sustainable development the cobweb;

- A world free from corruption is a universal dream;
- Poverty: universal and national problems;
- Safe, orderly and legal labor migration and efficient migration policy;
- Pandemic threats are cited.

In fact, today our scientists are finding a scientific basis for the damage of such threats to the development of the nation and society, aimed at causing spiritual chaos.

The concept of "moral threat". Sometimes it is difficult to understand the meaning of this concept.

Moral threats are a set of vices that create negative concepts, feelings, characteristics and qualities in the moral consciousness of a person. Because the word "threat" means danger, attack and violation. In this sense, moral threats are targeted attacks aimed at mentally and morally destroying a person.

In the conditions of the establishment of a new society, relations in social and economic life with different meanings, different goals, and different forms appear. Such colorful relations continue for Uzbekistan. In particular, moral threats organized consciously and purposefully from outside form the basis of such relations.

Today, spiritual threats are manifested in several forms.

It should be noted that spiritual threats are aimed at every person, regardless of language, religion and belief.

- The purpose of this first, breaking the spiritual and moral world of a person;
- secondly, to arouse the idea of malice towards one's homeland and society;
- thirdly, to change national moral values;
- fourth, to develop the ability to perceive the society of others as ideal;
- fifth, attack harmful habits.

If we pay attention, we will be sure that all kinds of spiritual threats are connected with an unhealthy lifestyle and that it is the most dangerous factor from an ideological point of view. Because it is based on a harmful idea aimed at derailing personal education.

The specific characteristics of moral threats are as follows:

First, spiritual threats are a complication of an unhealthy lifestyle;

Secondly, spiritual threats represent spiritual and moral vices is a set of subjective factors;

Thirdly, moral threats are a means of breaking the moral consciousness of the individual and the society aimed at derailing their lives and spreading an unhealthy lifestyle.

The impact of globalization on the countries of the world is also different.

This is the political, economic, informational, spiritual potential of the countries of the world depends on how it is. Each of the violent processes taking place in the world reducing the negative impact on a country and its positive impact

To strengthen the deeper understanding of the essence of this phenomenon, it is necessary to study its features. To him without studying this phenomenon in depth adaptation, it is impossible to change its direction accordingly.

Globalization is another process that cannot be studied deeply not to develop the strategy, tactics and technology of the country economy, culture, and spirituality to the torrent of the river flowing down from the mountain it's like abandoning a boat without a rudder.

These have an immediate effect on the minds of young people.

There are 1.8 billion young people in the world population. In particular, young people make up almost half of the population of Uzbekistan. As our President noted, the future of our planet depends on how our children grow up to be human beings. Our main task is to create the necessary conditions for young people to show their potential, to prevent the spread of the "virus" of moral threats and the idea of violence. For this, it is necessary to develop multilateral cooperation in social support of the young generation, protection of their rights and interests. The issue of protecting young people from various ideological attacks has always been an important issue. Especially in today's era of globalization, this issue is one of the number one problems for most countries. Because the processes of globalization are creating new opportunities for humanity, as well as unexpected problems. Threats and dangers against national identity and moral values are increasing day by day. People, especially young people, are masterfully instilled in the minds of people, especially young people, in various ways, thinking only about themselves, looking

lightly at work, family, and consumerism. One of them is the introduction of various harmful ideas and ideologies that are foreign to the thinking of our people. In such a dangerous situation, it is necessary to be alert and aware, to live thinking about the peace of our people and the interests of our country. Our head of state also emphasized that indifference and carelessness are the greatest danger, that there is a lack of education of intellectuals and public control to reduce the social problems faced today. with particular attention to the fact that youth education is a hugely responsible task before the whole nation: "If we do not give proper education to our child, every day, every minute, his behavior,

If we are not aware of their mood, if we do not train them in science and technology, if we do not find a decent job, we will lose this deposit, they say.

A threat to spirituality means a threat to the future. At a time when spiritual threats are on the rise, it is necessary to protect young people from the influence of internal and external threats, to form immunity against such negative evils. As we have decided to build a new Uzbekistan, we will overcome the spiritual threats that seriously threaten our achievement through the rich heritage of our ancestors and strong spirituality, education and training based on national values!

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